

A support to vertiport micro-location selection at airport for urban air mobility airport shuttle service

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ABSTRACT

Urban Air Mobility (UAM) services employing electric Vertical Take Off and Landing vehicles (eVTOL) will likely start in the next few years, and numerous research efforts are directed toward creating the necessary conditions for their successful implementation. Although vertiport location and vertiport capacity are recognized as key factors influencing UAM service performance, a notable research gap still remains in both areas. The vertiport location problem is addressed in the literature predominantly from the demand perspective, focusing on approximate macro-locations, e.g. centroids of the postal codes. Very limited research has addressed the micro-location level - determining the exact locations where vertiports should be built - which requires integrating other factors beyond demand. We aim to contribute to vertiport micro-location decisions by focusing on the hub nodes of the UAM airport shuttle network - vertiports at airports. Taking the airport operator's perspective, who will be responsible for planning and investing in such vertiports, we propose a framework for vertiport site selection that includes: selecting candidate sites, identifying relevant criteria, evaluating candidates against each criterion, and ranking them using a selected multi-criteria decision-making method. The study also contributes to capacity and cost estimation by introducing an online vertiport sizing and capacity tool that proposes the most favorable vertiport configuration(s) for any given area. The proposed framework is demonstrated through a case study of Madrid Airport. Beyond delivering a final ranking of ten candidate sites, a transparent evaluation process enables airport operators to understand the capacity-area trade-off, capacity capping in a single layout, and capacity increase by combining two layouts, the impact of vertiport type on cost, or landside/airside position on vertiport-to-terminal accessibility, as well as limitations with the current regulatory framework.

Introduction

Advancements in the development of Electric Vertical Take Off and Landing (eVTOL) vehicles have reignited the interest in Urban Air Mobility (UAM) services, such as transportation of people and goods, medical and emergency services (Holden and Goel, 2016). UAM operations are expected to start in the next few years across the globe (SMG Consulting, 2025a; SMG Consulting, 2025b), for instance in Abu Dubai and Saudi Arabia (Archer Aviation, 2025a; Joby Aviation, 2025a; Joby Aviation, 2025b), Rome (UrbanV, 2025), Guizhou (EHang, 2025), New York and Los Angeles (Delta, 2023), etc. There is already a considerable body of academic research supporting the successful implementation and initiation of UAM services: an overall review of current UAM literature is provided by Li et al. (2025), while Ahmed et al. (2025) assess the challenges and opportunities in UAM.

In the study on UAM acceptance (EASA, 2021) and the systematic

review on vertiport locations and capacity (Brunelli et al., 2023), the problem of vertiport location selection and associated vertiport capacity decisions are identified as two major challenges that can substantially impact the performance of UAM services. Sadrani et al. (2025) list a *lack of expertise in vertiport selection* as one of 26 potential barriers to UAM implementation. They define the *lack of expertise in vertiport selection as the limited knowledge and data in identifying a spatial vertiport network design to operate efficiently, while considering vehicle limitations and capturing the ensuing demand*, which reflects the state of the art in literature.

Thus far, literature has addressed the vertiport location problem primarily from a demand perspective. Long et al. (2023) provide a comprehensive literature review on demand analysis in UAM. They discuss several demand estimation methods supporting infrastructure placement for UAM, among which most researchers use clustering algorithms, often combined with other techniques, such as mode choice

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models, as most recently reported by Guo et al. (2025). Brunelli et al. (2023) also discuss the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and objective-based approaches, e.g. the Hub Location Problem, for approximate vertiport placement. They further argue that vertiport positioning is more relevant than the number of vertiports for travel time savings and successful UAM service. Guo et al. (2025) list key demand factors for vertiport placement in urban mobility systems addressed in the literature to date: alignment with travel demand patterns, seamless integration with existing transportation networks, and enhancement of metropolitan-wide accessibility.

To determine the exact locations where vertiports should be built, planners need to consider additional operational, cost, social, and environmental factors to complement demand-driven vertiport siting. Only recently, researchers have started to tackle the problem of selecting vertiport micro-locations. Petit and Ribeiro (2025) develop a framework to address the problem of vertiport siting for a middle-mile package delivery system, considering capacity, available land space, safety, and noise impact. Feldhoff and Soares Roque (2021) evaluate potential candidate vertiport sites at Cologne Bonn airport landside using five criteria: passenger accessibility, existing obstacles, noise impacts on adjacent buildings, expandability, applicability, and strategic availability, and they use qualitative assessment and subjective scores to rate alternatives. The research and practical question we aim to answer is: what are the necessary steps, criteria, quantitative model(s), and parameters for identifying, evaluating, and ranking micro-locations for vertiports?

We focus on the vertiport siting at airports for several reasons. First, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) identifies UAM airport shuttle service as one of the most likely initial use cases to be deployed in the EU for the passenger UAM segment (EASA, 2021). Second, airports are among the key stakeholders interested in vertiport development to expand their services, reduce ground congestion, and gain a strategic advantage by establishing hubs for feeder vertiports across urban areas in the emerging UAM network (Orlando International Airport, 2025; SEA Group, 2024). Archer Aviation, as one of the most prominent eVTOL manufacturers, has recently acquired an airport in Los Angeles (LA) to serve as its operational hub for its planned LA air taxi network (Archer Aviation 2025b). Lastly, unlike in cities, airports have sufficient land for vertiport development, and the possibility of placing vertiports at multiple locations. For instance, Orlando International Airport is already evaluating two potential sites for vertiport development (Orlando International Airport, 2025).

The goal of this research is to develop a framework for the evaluation and selection of vertiport micro-location at airports. We take the perspective of an airport operator who is responsible for planning and investing in vertiport(s) at the airport. The proposed framework supporting airport operators' decision-making includes four steps: the selection of candidate sites, followed by the identification of relevant criteria, evaluation of the candidates against each criterion, and ranking the candidates using a selected Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) method. It is built upon the state of the art in the areas of vertiport sizing, capacity, design, cost, and other relevant aspects related to siting vertiports at airports within the Multimodal Access for Intelligent Airports (MAIA) project (<https://maiaesarproject.eu/>). All major assumptions and input parameters were evaluated by external industry experts from various stakeholder groups, including airports, Air Navigation Service Providers, city governments, mobility consultancies, and academia. In total, nine experts attended a dedicated online webinar and completed the follow-up survey on June 7, 2024, while 21 experts, 11 in person and 10 online, attended the workshop on March 12, 2025, in Madrid. The meeting reports and survey results are available upon request.

The paper is structured as follows. First, we outline the first two steps: the selection of candidate sites and the identification of relevant criteria. We then detail the evaluation of the candidate sites against each of the selected criteria, followed by a proposed approach for ranking the candidates. We emphasize vertiport capacity and cost, as well as

accessibility from both ground level (additional travel time) and air (safety), as the most relevant decision-making criteria. To support vertiport capacity and cost evaluations, we developed an online tool that proposes the vertiport layout(s) that fit in a given area and result in the highest capacity under the smallest area, and allows a range of sensitivity and trade-off analysis. Finally, we demonstrate the ranking process using a real-world case study of Madrid Airport and end with the discussion and conclusions.

Identification of candidate sites and relevant criteria

Candidate vertiport sites

Our initial assumption is that a vertiport can be placed on the airport's landside or airside. Off-site locations in areas where the airport does not have permission to build were out of our scope. Literature favours locations on the airport landside for vertiport placement, such as the rooftops of parking garages, bus terminals, hotels, or ground-level car parks (Ahn and Hwang, 2022 – case study Gimpo Airport; Feldhoff and Soares Roque, 2021 – case study Cologne Bonn Airport). Only recently, Morscheck et al. (2025) considered one airside in addition to three landside locations at the Frankfurt Airport. Although locations on the airport airside have not received too much attention in the literature, airport operators consider them - Zurich Airport is planning (2030+) the reallocation of the general aviation area to the current heliport area (Zone West) and the expansion of the heliport, including electrical charging for possible future eVTOL operations (Flughafen Zürich, 2025). Heliports on the airport airside are common in practice and already ensure the safety of helicopter operations, which closely resemble future eVTOL operations. In addition to heliports, we considered portions of existing general aviation aprons, remote underutilized aircraft stands, or any adjacent areas, excluding military and cargo aprons.

Proposed locations and their pros and cons were subject to validation with the industry experts in the MAIA project.

Relevant criteria for vertiports at airport

Apart from being urban transportation nodes, vertiports are essentially airfields, which means that candidate site evaluation should meet different operational, social, cost, and environmental criteria, including, but not limited to: airspace conditions, weather issues, obstacles clearances, proximity to demand centres, ground access, land use and land value, noise impact, availability of utilities, etc. (ICAO, 1987).

Erkan and Elsharida (2019) and Alves et al. (2020) provide an overview of the criteria used in airport site selection. Erkan and Elsharida (2019) extracted 26 criteria, of which cost, environment, accessibility, and economics were most frequently used. Alves et al. (2020) identified 25 criteria from highly relevant books, regulatory documents, and papers. They argue that, in most cases, seven criteria are used: accessibility, obstacles to airspace, site dimensions, socially induced development, meteorology, noise, and urban development. Different sets of criteria apply for airfield site selection depending on its type, e.g. regional airport - Alves et al. (2020), second capital airport - Ding et al. (2011), military airport - Sennaroglu and Celebi (2018), heliport in central business district - Wieler (1958).

Only a handful of papers have analysed factors relevant to vertiport micro-location selection. Preis (2021) summarizes findings from a workshop with experts, who identified 69 factors that potentially affect the selection of appropriate areas for vertiports and grouped them into five categories: airspace clearance, building and architecture, community approval, surrounding transportation system, and others. In the systematic review on vertiport location and capacity, Brunelli et al. (2023) list three crucial factors for the evaluation of potential vertiport locations: physical space required for vertiports (which depends on eVTOL characteristics, size of passenger service buildings, eVTOL charging areas, and needs for future expansions), obstacle clearance,

and environmental constraints. Mercan et al. (2025) conduct a literature review first to identify criteria for evaluating the selection of vertiport locations within metropolitan areas and then use the best-worst method to rank them by importance, as follows (most to least importance): air traffic management, cost, safety, consumer acceptance, vertiport design, aircraft features, traffic congestion, and meteorological conditions.

Previous studies focused on identifying the relevant criteria influencing vertiport location, but none have addressed vertiports at airports, except Feldhoff and Soares Roque (2021), who identified the following criteria as relevant: accessibility, obstacles, noise, expandability, cost ('applicability'), and strategic availability. Morscheck et al. (2025) mention *passenger transit time, capital expenses, impacts on airport landside and airside operations, and time to realise* as criteria for selecting the vertiport at the airport, but do not provide a methodology for scoring and evaluation.

Based on previous studies, the most common criteria for any airfield (vertiports included) location are: physical space (capacity), obstacles, airspace (safety), environment (noise), cost, accessibility, and meteorology. Moreover, for the wider adoption of the UAM service, citizens' and future UAM users' acceptance is critical (EASA, 2021). Apart from noise and safety, widely recognized in aviation, other factors have been raised from the UAM concept of operations at low altitudes within densely populated areas - privacy concerns, visual pollution, security, etc.

Due to differences in roles (feeders vs. hubs) and positions (densely populated urban areas vs. airport proximity), there are notable differences in the criteria relevant to vertiport micro-locations in urban areas and to vertiport placement at airports.

Noise is a highly relevant problem for vertiport placement in urban areas and even more so for the design of routes connecting these vertiports, since eVTOL operations are conducted at low altitudes, affecting people along the entire route, not only at vertiports. While noise is important for route design to connect the city and the airport, it is not relevant for vertiports in the airport's proximity, where eVTOL noise is masked by aircraft landing and take-off noise. In addition, the proximity of the airport, due to very high exposure to aircraft noise, is planned as an industrial zone, while objects associated with airport activities or any remaining or new residential objects must have adequate acoustic insulation - all being measures to mitigate noise impact.

Similarly, other community acceptance criteria, such as privacy concerns, visual pollution, or security, have no significant influence on vertiport placement at an airport. Vertiports at airports will be built on top of existing infrastructures or in areas where the airport operator holds permission to build. This means that land use and land value are similar or even the same for most micro-locations and will have little to no effect on vertiport cost, unlike in cities with high land price variation across different areas.

The same applies to meteorological conditions (wind, visibility) and obstacles, which do not vary significantly across candidate sites at the airport, as they may in urban areas. However, they need to be considered when planning arrival and departure corridors.

For the selection of vertiport micro-location at airports, we narrow the list of relevant factors to safety, capacity, cost, and accessibility. Vertiports at airports must provide sufficient capacity at an acceptable cost to the airport operator, located in proximity to terminal(s) to ensure competitiveness with other modes of transport (accessibility), but not so close as to affect the safety and capacity of aircraft operation. The most recent publication, presenting a detailed review of vertiport siting methods and approaches (Wu et al., 2025), recognizes vertiport capacity and vertiport cost as key factors affecting the feasibility of vertiport siting, even from a vertiport network perspective.

Vertiport candidate sites evaluation and ranking

We introduce quantitative methods to evaluate selected factors (capacity, cost, and accessibility), limiting qualitative evaluation to areas

where underdeveloped regulations and concept of operations do not yet allow quantitative analysis (safety). So far, only Feldhof and Soares (2021) address the problem of vertiport micro-location at airports through a qualitative assessment of selected criteria.

The primary concern in vertiport site selection is the safe integration of vertiport and eVTOL operations with existing aircraft operations. The complexity of integrating eVTOL operations in and around airports will be affected by the vertiport's micro-location, including its position relative to the runway layout, typical runway configurations in use, prevailing winds, obstacles, the direction of eVTOL operations, and other conditions. Higher complexity implies lower location attractiveness. Presently, neither the eVTOL concept of operations nor the vertiport-specific regulatory framework is fully defined, to allow a quantitative approach to complexity. Therefore, the vertiport site selection at the airport begins with triage, as shown in Fig. 1, where airport planners and stakeholders can dismiss candidate locations based on their relative position to the runway system, terminal building, and urban area.

For candidate sites that pass triage, the next step is to evaluate them against relevant criteria (capacity, cost, accessibility). We develop a tool to estimate capacity and propose vertiport configurations based on the candidate site area. We then estimate the vertiport cost of the proposed configuration based on the required area, the number of gates, and the vertiport type (roof/ground). Vertiport accessibility is measured as the time required for passengers to reach the terminal building from the vertiport site, on landside or airside.

The final step is to rank the candidates based on the criteria values and associated weights using the selected multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method.

As the concept of operations, regulations, or requirements for eVTOL operations mature, the decision-making process can be expanded to include additional criteria.

Vertiport integration into airport environment

Arguably, the biggest challenge related to vertiport placement at airports is ensuring the safe integration of eVTOL operations with aircraft operations. The latest review on regulatory frameworks (Hijazeen et al., 2025) confirms a significant regulatory gap in vertiport safety and operational requirements, particularly with respect to safe integration with airport operations.

The most recent United States Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) guidelines on vertiports cover this topic only at a high level (Federal Aviation Administration, 2024). The FAA presently recognizes three options for vertiport placement at airports: adjacent to a runway, between (independent) parallel runways, and at the end of a runway, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

When siting a vertiport adjacent to a runway, it is essential to consider the lateral separation between the Final Approach and Take Off (FATO) area and runway centreline. FATO located within 213 m of a runway centreline is likely to affect both runway and vertiport operations and require continuous wake turbulence mitigation and close air traffic control (ATC) coordination. FATO-runway separation between 213 m and 762 m may permit greater operational independence, although vertiport capacity remains sensitive to aircraft type, traffic density, and flight path geometry. A separation distance of 762 m or more provides the greatest potential for independent operations with minimal interference to runway traffic.

Vertiports located between parallel runways introduce additional ATC complexity, as VTOL aircraft must either overfly or operate parallel to active runways before crossing extended centrelines, often resulting in indirect routings or increased delay.

Vertiports located off the end of runways, particularly along extended runway centrelines, impose the most restrictive conditions, as VTOL aircraft must maintain vertical separation of at least 152 m below arriving or departing runway traffic, increasing to 305 m when

Fig. 1. Overall approach for vertiport candidate sites evaluation and ranking.

Fig. 2. Siting vertiports on or near existing airports (Federal Aviation Administration, 2024).

operating underneath heavy or super aircraft. Where these separations cannot be maintained, vertiport operations may be delayed or constrained.

The most penalizing vertiport locations are those placed closer than 213 m to runway centreline, or such where crossing the runway or arriving/departing traffic cannot be avoided.

EASA’s vertiport guidelines mention only the edge-to-edge separation between FATO and taxiway/runway ranging from 60 m to 250 m, depending on the aircraft weight category (EASA, 2022).

There are also only a few academic publications dealing with the safe integration of eVTOL operations at airports. Straubinger et al. (2021) recognize the eVTOL operations integration into airport airspace as one of the major challenges for UAM airport shuttle service. They provide a high-level discussion, including the integration of eVTOLs into arrival patterns versus runway or approach path crossing, as well as open (independent) versus closely-spaced parallel runway layouts. Vascik and Hansman (2021) propose solutions for vertiport integration in the airport environment, suggesting off-site FATO and long hovering to the terminal to avoid any interference with aircraft operations. Ahrenhold et al. (2021) propose three different integration methods for eVTOL flight routes to Hamburg Airport, including approaches to the vertiport located by the terminal, the runway, and the hangar area. Morschcheck et al. (2025) design corridors for eVTOL access to four Frankfurt Airport sites: one off-site, two by the terminals, and one on the airside.

Previous studies focus on airspace, but we also address other issues that may be relevant, such as interference with aircraft surface movements when connecting an airside vertiport to the airport terminal.

Due to the lack of an operational concept definition for eVTOLs and vertiport regulations, quantifying interference between future eVTOLs and aircraft based on assumed concept of operations and separation rules would likely introduce significant uncertainty into the complexity

metrics at this point. Furthermore, this process would be highly case sensitive. Therefore, we define a set of soft rules based on general principles applicable to any airport.

We assess the vertiport candidate site’s position relative to the terminal system, urban area (city), and runway system to determine whether to accept or reject the candidate site. Locations that would significantly degrade the efficiency of vertiport operations we consider unacceptable for a vertiport serving as a hub node in the UAM airport shuttle network. These are locations that would require crossings of the active runways (on the ground or in the air), placed closer than the minimum advised distances to the runway centreline, or directly underneath arriving and departing paths.

Soft rules for the initial triage of candidate sites, summarized below, are illustrated in Fig. 3, which shows examples using four basic runway configurations (single runway, closely spaced parallel runways, crossing and converging runways).

Vertiport location relative to the terminal system. (A terminal system refers to one or multiple physically connected terminals.) Placing the vertiport and terminal system on the same side of the runway system is considered an acceptable option. This option allows the most direct vertiport-to-terminal transfer without unnecessary rerouting. Otherwise, the vertiport-to-terminal transfer may be excessively long - for landside candidates, or unacceptable from a safety perspective if it requires crossing an active runway - for airside candidates. In this case, we suggest dismissing the candidate.

Vertiport location relative to the city. When a vertiport and the city are located on the same side of the runway system, at an acceptable distance between FATO and runway centreline, interference with aircraft take-offs and landings is minimized, and such locations are considered acceptable. If vertiport and the city are located on opposite sides of the runway(s), vertiport operations would be required to cross

Runway layout	Single	Closely-spaced parallel	Crossing	Converging
Vertiport-terminal position				
Vertiport-city position				
Vertiport-runway system position*				
<p>*Case specific – accounts for runway system layout, preferential runway configuration, FATO-runway distance, arriving and departing procedures, existing heliport location and helicopter routes, flying-over apron and taxiways, etc.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: center; gap: 20px;"> accept conditionally accept reject </div>				

Fig. 3. Soft rules for vertiport candidate site triage, illustrated on four basic runway configurations.

the runway, or eVTOL route length would be significantly longer to avoid such crossings. These are the reasons to dismiss such candidate sites. For any other relative position, e.g. when the city is located in the direction of the runways, or the vertiport is between two runways, where eVTOL paths may at some point intersect arriving or departing paths, the location should be conditionally accepted. The vertiport position relative to the runway system becomes more relevant for the final decision.

Vertiport location relative to the runway system. Includes position of the vertiport in the context of runway configuration, preferential directions in use, FATO-runway separation, arriving and departing procedures, existing heliports and helicopter routes, flying over apron or taxiway, etc. This issue is case-specific and should include specific runway operations rules and vertiport operations rules. A more accurate assessment will be possible once the regulatory framework begins to address this issue in greater detail. So far, we assume that locations closer than the minimum advised distance to the runway centreline (250 m in EASA’s guidelines) or directly beneath the arrival and departure paths are unacceptable. Locations between two active runways, or if arriving and departing paths must be intersected at some point, are considered conditionally acceptable.

Even with a well-developed regulatory basis, the triage step based on soft rules should remain to eliminate unfeasible locations before proceeding to case-specific procedure design and more sophisticated complexity scoring.

At this stage, we propose subjectively chosen values to quantify ‘complexity’, where acceptable is rated 1.0 (neutral for the composite score), conditional is rated 0.4 (reduces the score, but it is not disqualifying), and unacceptable is rated 0.0 (zeroes out the score and disqualifies the option). Ratings for three sub-criteria are combined by multiplication, to yield the composite score for use in the MCDM analysis.

In Table 1, we illustrate triage process on the Brussels Airport example, with two candidate sites – the general aviation apron and the cargo apron.

Vertiport capacity

Each candidate site on the airport landside or airside is characterized by available area for vertiport development. Vertiport layouts that fit within an available area may yield different capacity figures and incur different infrastructure and development costs.

We developed the Vertiport Sizing and Capacity (VSC) tool, available online at <http://vsctool.sf.bg.ac.rs/>. The tool enables fast capacity estimation and selection of the most favourable vertiport layout for each candidate site. The VSC tool offers two core functionalities: Vertiport Capacity and Area (VCA) and Propose Vertiport Configuration (PVC).

The VCA allows users to calculate vertiport capacity as the number of eVTOL operations per hour and determine the area required for different vertiport layouts, as illustrated in Fig. 4. It supports sensitivity analysis by adjusting input parameters related to eVTOL design specifications, vertiport operations, charging scenarios, and vertiport layout options.

For specified vertiport area dimensions, the PVC searches across all layouts and a range of gates (2–10) to recommend a vertiport configuration with the highest capacity and minimal area required, as shown in Fig. 5.

The tool supports airport operators’ informed decision-making by allowing sensitivity analysis to input data, understanding capacity-area and capacity-cost trade-offs, overall capacity capping for each layout, or a combination of the layouts to maximize capacity in larger areas.

In previous studies, vertiport capacity modelling for different vertiport layouts mainly relied on integer programming (e.g. Vascik and Hansman, 2019; Preis, 2021; Ahn and Hwang, 2022, 2023). All studies address capacity-area dependency, while Vascik and Hansman (2019) and Preis (2021, 2023) highlight the importance of analysing both maximum throughput for a given area and area requirements for a targeted throughput. Vascik and Hansman (2019) and Preis (2021, 2023) use heliport design guidelines to estimating vertiport footprints, while only Ahn and Hwang (2022) refer to vertiport design guidelines published by EASA and FAA in 2022.

We develop a vertiport capacity estimation model based on well-established analytical model for estimating theoretical runway capacity (Blumstein, 1959) and apron capacity estimations (Mirković and Tošić, 2014, 2017), adapted for vertiport operations and assumed

Table 1
Assessing vertiport candidate site position relative to terminal(s), city(s) and runway(s), Brussels Airport example.

V ID	V2T	V2C	RWY	overall
1 – GA apron	Vertiport and terminal are located on the same side of all three runways. 1.0	The city is placed in the direction of extended centerlines of the runways 07L/25R and 07R/25L. 0.4	Vertiport is placed between independent parallel runways, at 550m from RWY 07L/25R and 850m from extended edge of the RWY 07R/25L. Preferential runways in use are 25R and 25L, in which case there is very low possibility for interference between arriving aircraft and eVTOLs. When opposite direction is in use due to wind, there is possible interference when 07L is used for arrivals. 0.4	0.16
2 – cargo apron	Vertiport and terminal are located on opposite sides of the runway 07L/25R. 0.0	The city is placed in the direction of extended centerlines of the runways 07L/25R and 07R/25L. 0.4	Vertiport is placed adjacent to the runway, at the distance 250m from the runway edge, providing the EASA’s required separation. 1.0	0.0

operational policies. The vertiport sizing model relies on the current EASA’s vertiport design guidelines (EASA, 2022) and adopts various vertiport configurations described in the literature (Ahn and Hwang, 2022; Schweiger et al., 2022; Vascik and Hansman, 2019).

Appendix 2 details the inputs to the VSC Tool including eVTOL parameters relevant for airport sizing and operations, vertiport design requirements relevant for simultaneous operations, vertiport operations, amended by passenger processing and charging scenarios, and vertiport layouts. Previous studies conduct vertiport capacity analyses using fixed or ranges-based of values for arrival, departure, taxi, and turnaround times. The VSC Tool expands the set of input variables and allow users to perform sensitivity analyses by adjusting these variables without replicating the model. Unlike previous studies, we calculate taxi times using

taxi distances (sensitive to layout and eVTOL D-value) and taxi speed (which can be varied), and we derive turnaround times from passenger processing and vehicle charging times.

Appendix 3 details analytical models for estimating vertiport theoretical capacity and calculating vertiport area. We assume that vertiport elements - FATO, gate, and taxiway – are each used by only one eVTOL at a time. Accounting for the impact of sequential taxiing on the exchange of arriving and departing eVTOLs prevents overestimating capacity, particularly in layouts with a single FATO.

For the selected input parameters (Appendix 2), the VSC tool, VCA functionality, returns:

Fig. 4. Illustration of the VCA functionality within VSC tool.

Fig. 5. Illustration of the PVC functionality within VSC tool.

- 1) area parameters: length (L), width (W), total area, area under FATO and gates, fill factor calculated as a portion of the total area occupied by FATOs and gates, L to W ratio,
- 2) capacity: arrival, departure, gate, and overall,
- 3) average taxi distance/ time and
- 4) area per operation per hour.

The user can select any of the six layouts, and the results are calculated and presented for a range of gates.

Fig. 6 shows an example output from the VCA with default inputs, for a linear configuration with 2 FATOs. We can see that an area of 300 m x 90 m is required to accommodate a linear vertiport with two FATOs and 10 gates. We also find that the maximum overall capacity of 80 ops/h is achieved with 6 gates. Providing additional gates will not increase overall capacity, meaning that, at this point, FATO capacity becomes more constraining than gate capacity. Vascik and Hansman (2019) support the same finding by analysing average FATO and gate utilization.

Gates	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Length	112.5	112.5	120	150	180	210	240	270	300
Width	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
Total Area	10125	10125	10800	13500	16200	18900	21600	24300	27000
Area Under FATO and Gates	2826	3533	4239	4946	5652	6359	7065	7772	8478
Fill Factor	3.6	2.9	2.5	2.7	2.9	3	3.1	3.1	3.2
LW Ratio	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.7	2	2.3	2.7	3	3.3
Capacity Arr	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Capacity Dep	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Capacity Gate	14.5	21.8	28.9	35.3	41.5	47.5	53.2	58.6	63.9
Capacity Overall	29	43.6	57.8	70.6	80	80	80	80	80
Avg Taxi Distance	101.25	101.25	105	120	135	150	165	180	195
Taxi Time	72.9	72.9	75.6	86.4	97.2	108	118.8	129.6	140.4
Area Per Ops Per Hour	349	232	187	191	203	236	270	304	338

Fig. 6. Vertiport capacity and area output the for linear layout with 2 FATOs, and default inputs.

The relationship between available area and vertiport capacity for different layouts is shown in Fig. 7.

The second functionality, PVC, returns vertiport layouts that could be fitted within the available area of the candidate vertiport site. The tool searches across all feasible options, i.e., layouts and variations in the number of gates, and for each layout, proposes a configuration with the maximum capacity under the smallest area (i.e. the smallest number of gates). An example of the resulting capacity and utilized area for the available area of 180 m x 140 m is shown in Fig. 8. A linear layout with two FATOs and 6 gates returns the highest capacity of 80 ops/h while occupying the smallest area, 16,200 m².

In addition to basic outputs, the VSC tool also supports additional analysis.

As discussed, the overall capacity constraint shifts from gates to FATOs beyond a certain number of gates, as shown in Fig. 9 (for the satellite layout, above 3 gates; and for pier layout with two FATOs, above 7 gates). Any further increase in overall can be achieved only by increasing the number of FATOs, i.e. by combining two layouts. For this reason, the VSC tool (PVC functionality) supports double-layout analysis for larger areas.

In the case of satellite layout (Fig. 9, left), we can see the impact of (sequential) taxiing on mixed-mode operations (arrival/departure) on a single FATO - capacity decreases when the number of gates exceeds 3. Longer taxiing times increase idle periods for FATOs and gates, making single-FATO layouts highly underutilized if a number of gates exceeds 3 or 4.

For vertiports at airports acting as network hubs, off-peak periods may impose higher requirements on eVTOL staging. While the PVC functionality aims to propose layouts for maximum throughput to satisfy peak-hour demand, the VCA functionality can be used to identify the option with the maximum number of stands for staging purposes.

Vertiport cost

Vertiport development cost includes land acquisition, site preparation and construction, permits, equipment, etc. Some vertiports in urban and suburban areas may also require a terminal building, which is not the case with airport vertiports, where passengers could use airport terminals for processing.

We examine the construction costs and installation of electrical chargers, assuming that other costs do not differ across candidate airport locations to generate a tangible difference for ranking purposes. Vertiport construction costs are calculated based on the utilized area of the selected option, the number of chargers, and the vertiport type, which can be on airside, elevated, or rooftop.

Landside vertiport construction costs (*COSTL*) depend on the type of vertiport. The cost of the proposed vertiport layout is calculated based on the utilized area and the number of gates that need to be equipped with chargers:

Fig. 7. Relationship between area and capacity for six layouts, default inputs.

$$COSTL = proposed_vertiport_layout_area \cdot unit_construction_cost + N \cdot charger_unit_price$$

Vertiports located at airport aprons (*COSTA*) do not have associated construction costs but only costs related to repainting the markings:

$$COSTA = marking_cost + N \cdot charger_unit_price$$

There is no reliable source for the unit cost of constructing rooftop vertiports. We rely on consultations with industry experts and practitioners who estimate that rooftop heliport construction costs are 3–5 times higher than construction costs for a ground heliport.

Unit costs are derived from the NASA commissioned study (Black & Veatch and National Institute of Aerospace, 2018), corrected for the inflation rate 2018–2025 and the currency conversion (USD to EUR):

- unit cost of the heliport pavement: 80 EUR/m²,
- the cost of charger installation on ground: 560,130 EUR per charger (derived from the scenario with three electrified pads),
- the cost of charger installation on the rooftop: 547,163 EUR per charger (derived from the scenario of the electrified pad at the existing garage).

As with the other input parameters and assumptions, these cost estimates were also subject to experts' validation in the MAIA project. Some other cost estimates, e.g. by McKinsey & Company (2020), suggest a significantly lower cost, ranging from 200 K to 800 K EUR, for vertiports with up to 3–9 pads (FATOs and gates). In literature, vertiport cost ranges from several hundred thousand to several million EUR, depending on assumptions, number of FATOs, gates, etc. (Schweiger and Preis, 2022). Fig. 10 shows the trade-off between capacity and cost of ground and elevated vertiports across layouts.

Additional travel time

Accessibility to the airport for eVTOL aircraft should be as direct as possible, ideally with the access vertiport placed as close to the terminal as access points for competing means of transport (e.g. taxis). If the vertiport location requires that passengers need to use another mode of transportation, the transfer to and from the terminal should be provided under the same quality of service, e.g. a premium car transfer without additional waiting times.

We calculate additional vertiport-to-terminal travel time based on the travel distance and average travel speed. Traveling from the vertiport to the terminal is via the public road network for vertiport sites located on the landside (Fig. 11 left, Zurich Airport) and via service roads on the apron for vertiport sites located on the airside (Fig. 11 right, Brussels Airport). Speed is assumed to be 35 km/h on public roads and 20 km/h on airside service roads.

Transfer times for landside locations can be negatively affected by road congestion or level changes at rooftop vertiports. Nevertheless, they can benefit from existing rapid connections (e.g. Automated People Movers linking remote parking with terminals). At airside locations, multiple stop-and-go points along aircraft movement paths on the airport apron negatively affect transfer time. Still, they offer the benefit of shorter processing through a business aviation terminal or similar premium services.

If an airport has more than one terminal system, like Madrid Airport with Terminals 1, 2, and 3 composing one system and Terminals 4 and 4S another, the average accessibility time is calculated as a weighted average, where the weights represent the proportion of passengers (excluding transfers) using each of the terminal systems.

Candidate sites ranking

When the number of candidate sites is low, e.g. up to three, the

Results

Fig. 8. Proposed vertiport configurations for area 180 m × 140 m.

Fig. 9. Overall capacity constraint shifting from gate capacity to FATO capacity, for satellite and pier with 2 FATOs layouts.

Fig. 10. Capacity-cost trade-off for all layouts, ground vertiport (left) and elevated vertiport (right).

vertiport site can be selected by experts based on the values of the three criteria, without needing any MCDM method.

For a larger number of sites, some of the MCDM methods could help in making the selection. The focus of our study is rather on the evaluation of the criteria i.e. estimating the values for each criterion, while for the final ranking the airport operator may decide on any MCDM method.

We apply the Simple Additive Weight (SAW) method to rank candidate sites. The overall score for candidate i is calculated as:

$$R_i = \sum_j n_{ij} \cdot w_j$$

where

n_{ij} is the normalized value of the candidate i for the criterion j ,
 r_{ij} is the original value of the candidate i for the criterion j and
 w_j is the weight of the j^{th} criterion.

We compare four different techniques for the normalization of the

Fig. 11. Vertiport-to-terminal routes via public roads (left) and apron service roads (right).

Table 2
Normalization of the cost and benefit criteria.

Normalization	Benefit criteria	Cost criteria
min max	$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij} - r_{min}}{r_{max} - r_{min}}$	$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{max} - r_{ij}}{r_{max} - r_{min}}$
max	$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{r_{max}}$	$n_{ij} = 1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{r_{max}}$
sum	$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{\sum r_{ij}}$	$n_{ij} = 1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{\sum r_{ij}}$
vector	$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum r_{ij}^2}}$	$n_{ij} = 1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum r_{ij}^2}}$

benefit and cost criteria (Table 2).

To the best of our knowledge, there are no publications that suggest weights of the criteria for the vertiport site selection problem. In general, the weighting of the criteria can rely on decision-makers’ preferences in a subjective approach or can use values from the decision matrix to objectively determine weights; the two approaches can be combined. In this study, we use equal weights as a benchmark, Entropy weights based on dispersion of values for a criterion, and CRITIC—Criteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation weights based on dispersion of values and intercriteria correlation with equal weights benchmark (Table 3).

Case study: Madrid airport

With the industry experts, we identify ten candidate sites for vertiports at Madrid Airport (MAD), as shown in Fig. 12. Five sites are located near Terminals 1, 2, and 3. Three potential sites are car parks located on the landside (V-L1-T123, V-L2-T123, and V-L7-T123), and two are on the airside – a portion of the general aviation apron (V-A1-T123) and the isolated apron (V-A2-T123). Four out of five sites near Terminal 4 + 4S are located on the landside: two car parks (V-L3-T4 and V-L6-T4), one garage (V-L4-T4), and one unpaved area (V-L5-T4). The fifth candidate is a portion of the apron located between Terminal 4 and the existing helicopter FATO (V-A3-T4).

Considering three soft constraints for the triage of the candidate sites, all sites are acceptable in terms of expected interference with aircraft operations:

- vertiport-terminal system position – same side of the runway, no runway crossings on the vertiport-to-terminal transfer path (1.0)
- vertiport-city position – same side of the runway, low to no interference with aircraft routes (1.0),
- vertiport-runway system position – sites are not placed in between independent parallel runways or closer than 250 m from the runway or taxiway edge (1.0).

Using Google Earth, we measured the maximum dimensions of length (L) and width (W) of the rectangular area(s) that can be fitted

Table 3
Entropy and CRITICS weights.

Entropy weights	CRITIC weights
Proportion matrix: $p_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}}{\sum n_{ij}}$	Z-score: $z_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij} - \bar{n}_j}{\sigma_j}$
Entropy value: $E_j = -k \sum p_{ij} \ln(p_{ij})$	where \bar{n}_j – the mean of criterion j across all alternatives σ_j – the standard deviation of criterion j
$k = \frac{1}{\ln(n)}$	Correlation between criteria:
where n – number of candidates	$r_{jk} = \frac{\sum z_{ij} \cdot z_{ik}}{n}$
Degree of diversification: $D_j = 1 - E_j$	where n – number of candidates
Weight: $w_j = \frac{D_j}{\sum D_j}$	Conflict and redundancy: $C_j = \sum (1 - r_{jk})$
	Information value: $I_j = \sigma_j \cdot C_j$
	Weight: $w_j = \frac{I_j}{\sum I_j}$

Fig. 12. Candidate sites at Madrid Airport.

within each candidate site (Table 4, column 3). For each candidate site, the VSC tool proposes a vertiport configuration with the highest capacity that requires the smallest area (Table 4, columns 4, 5, and 6, respectively). For the selected vertiport configuration, the cost of the vertiport is calculated based on the number of gates, utilized area, and type of vertiport (Table 4, columns 4, 6, and 7).

The process is demonstrated in detail using the V-L3-T4 site as an example. The total area is split into two sub-areas, measuring 115 m x 100 m and 220 m x 200 m. Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 show the most favourable configurations for each sub-area, respectively. For the first sub-area, a linear configuration with 2 FATOs and 3 gates yields the highest capacity of 41.8 ops/h. For the second sub-area, a linear layout with 2 FATOs is again a favourable layout, but with 6 gates in this case, and a capacity of 80 ops/h. This configuration has the same capacity as LEIDT with 5 gates but occupies a smaller area (16,200 m² vs. 22,500 m²). To enable independent operations, two layouts are merged in a way to bring gates inside and FATOs on the outside edges (illustrated in Fig. 15), allowing landings/take-offs without overflying gate area, which allows a total capacity of 121.8 ops/h.

Total cost of the two independent vertiports, both with linear layout with 2 FATOs, one with 3, and the second with 6 gates is:

$$(10,125 + 16,200) \cdot 240 + (3 + 6) \cdot 547,163 = 11.2 \text{ million EUR}$$

We can see from Table 4 that the maximum capacity is usually reached under a significantly smaller area than the available area (e.g. L1-T123 available area 58,336 m², area consumed by the configuration with the maximum capacity 16,200 m²). The table also shows that the cost of airside vertiports can be significantly lower, as they already have paved surfaces with sufficient load-bearing capacity.

The third criterion, travel time, is determined by the vertiport-to-terminal travel distance and the average speed of 35 km/h on public roads and 20 km/h on apron service roads. Distances and times are shown in Table 5. The weighted average time is calculated as the vertiport-to-T123 and vertiport-to-T4 times adjusted for the proportion of passengers using each of the terminal systems. In the MAD case, this share is approximately 50 %-50 % based on the number of commercial passengers by destination, extracted from Aena’s statistics for 2024.

Average vertiport-to-terminal time shows that at large airports, such as Madrid Airport, airside locations can come under penalty of long

transfer times when located at airside perimeters.

We use the SAW method for ranking the candidate sites. Capacity is a benefit criterion, while cost and accessibility are cost criteria. We use the same weights for all three criteria (0.33) as a benchmark. Fig. 16 compares the ranking using four techniques to normalize criteria values. Two vertiport candidates are ranked the top two, regardless of the normalization technique employed. These are: V-L5-T4, which is the large unpaved area by T4, located also relatively close to T123; and V-L2-T123, which is the short-term parking by T123 (direct access), with good accessibility to T4 as well. The airside candidate site V-A2-T123 is ranked last, penalized by extremely unfavourable travel times to both T123 and T4.

The rank of other candidates is stable, varying by up to two positions. The exception is V-L6-T4, best ranked 4th and worst ranked 9th. This candidate is well connected to terminals, with high capacity, but at a very high cost, double compared to V-L5-T4 with the same capacity.

We also check the sensitivity of the results to weights, using the min-max SAW method (Fig. 17). Entropy weights method returns the following weights: capacity 0.51, AVG time 0.23, and cost 0.26, while CRITIC weights are: capacity 0.34, AVG time 0.27, and cost 0.38. CRITICS weights are evenly balanced, while entropy weights give higher importance to capacity and lower to time and cost. The Entropy method weights could be related to cases where stakeholders expect very high demand for UAM airport shuttle service and want to give much more importance to capacity, compared to accessibility and cost. While some airports might face such cases, in the end, the experts should review and, if necessary, amend the weights obtained from objective value-based methods.

The ranking provides valuable information to decision-makers, but the final decision should take into consideration other locally specific issues. The capacity figures represent the maximum throughput, which reflects the potential for meeting a future demand increase and is not necessarily utilized in the initial stages of UAM airport shuttle service introduction. Note that, for example, V-L5-T4 has a capacity of 160 ops/h, which is the same as that of the V-L2-T123 and V-L4-T4 together. Since demand for the service strongly depends on the total travel time, in the case of spacious airports like Madrid Airport, a potentially more favourable strategy would be to develop two vertiport sites, one for each terminal system (T123 and T4). Such a decision would be associated

Table 4
MAD candidate sites - area, capacity and cost.

Candidate site	Available area (m ²)	L x W that can be fitted (m)	VSC Tool proposed layout	Vertiport capacity (ops/h)	Proposed layout area (m ²)	Vertiport type	Vertiport cost (mill. EUR)
V-A1-T123	11,250	150 × 75	finger 2 FATO 3 gates	39.0	9000	airside	1.7
V-A2-T123	30,992	210 × 105	linear 2 FATO 6 gates	80.0	16,200	airside	3.4
V-A3-T4	42,163	350 × 100	finger 2 FATO 7 gates	80.0	16,200	airside	3.9
V-L1-T123	58,336	180 × 180	linear 2 FATO 6 gates	80.0	16,200	new rooftop	7.2
V-L2-T123	13,593	2 × 90 × 70	2 x satellite with 3 gates	64.4	10,800	new rooftop	5.9
V-L3-T4*	55,763	115 × 100+ 220 × 200	linear 2 FATO 3 gates linear 2 FATO 6 gates	121.8	26,325	new rooftop	11.2
V-L4-T4	51,993	660 × 40	multi-function 8 FATOs	95.6	18,225	rooftop (existing)	9.2
V-L5-T4	82,626	360 × 220: 2 × 220 × 180 2 × 360 × 110	2 x linear 2 FATO 6 gates	160.0	32,400	unpaved ground	9.3
V-L6-T4	54,575	330 × 150 330 × 90+ 330 × 60 150 × 150+ 180 × 150	finger 2 FATO 7 gates 2 x finger 2 FATO 6 gates	160.0	45,000	new rooftop	17.4
V-L7-T123	20,892	100 × 100	2 x LEIDT 6 gates satellite with 3 gates	32.2	5400	new rooftop	2.9

First Area Parameters

Length 1	115
Width 1	100

Results

Fig. 13. Proposed vertiport configurations for area 115 m × 100 m.

Second Area Parameters

Length 2	220
Width 2	200

Results

Fig. 14. Proposed vertiport configurations for area 220 m × 200 m.

with somewhat higher cost, where instead of one ground vertiport, one would be at the existing rooftop and another at the new rooftop, but with the benefit of reduced additional travel times, hence higher service attractiveness and, expectedly, faster growing demand.

Discussion and conclusions

In this paper, we present a framework for vertiport micro-location selection at airports. The proposed framework can be used by airport operators in early-stage vertiport planning as a structured screening and prioritization approach, enabling transparent comparison of multiple candidate locations under varying operational, spatial, and regulatory constraints.

The main outcome of the proposed approach is the final ranking of the candidate vertiport sites. However, all four steps of the process contribute to informed decision-making for airport operators. Understanding the capacity-area and capacity-cost trade-offs, capacity capping for different vertiport layouts, using double layouts to maximize

capacity of large areas, cost sensitivity to type of vertiport and layout, impact of landside/airside position to vertiport-to-terminal accessibility, sensitivity to method and weights of the criteria, as well as drawbacks originating from the gaps in regulations - all ensure that airport operator can adapt the decision making to its own scope, preferences and constraints.

One of the significant challenges at airports is safely integrating vertiports and eVTOL operations with existing airfields used by commercial airlines. Presently, due to the underdeveloped concept of operations and regulations, we cannot credibly assess the feasibility of different options or estimate a complexity indicator for integrating eVTOL operations. Therefore, we propose a qualitative assessment of the vertiport location relative to the terminal, city, and runways, to triage initial candidates, employing a simple quantification to distinguish between acceptable, conditional, and unacceptable rates. We elaborate on the rationale for selecting capacity, cost, and accessibility as the key quantitative criteria in a multi-criteria ranking of vertiport candidates at airports. Placing a vertiport closer to the terminal, or even at the airside,

Fig. 15. Merging two proposed vertiport layouts to allow independent operations.

Table 5
MAD candidate sites vertiport-to-terminal transfer distance and time.

Candidate site	Distance to T2 (m)	Distance to T4 (m)	Time to T2 (min)	Time to T4 (min)	AVG time (min)
V-A1-T123	1850	5900	5.55	17.70	11.60
V-A2-T123	3850	7900	11.55	23.70	17.60
V-A3-T4	5900	700	17.70	2.10	9.90
V-L1-T123	850	6700	1.46	11.49	6.50
V-L2-T123	0	5200	0.00	8.91	4.50
V-L3-T4	6600	3500	11.31	6.00	8.70
V-L4-T4	6200	0	10.63	0.00	5.30
V-L5-T4	4000	1900	6.86	3.26	5.10
V-L6-T4	3100	3000	5.31	5.14	5.20
V-L7-T123	1100	5600	1.89	9.60	5.70

could be more attractive, as it enhances passenger comfort and has minimal negative impact on total travel time, thereby ensuring the UAM service competitiveness with other modes of transport.

Our major contribution is the development of an analytical model for vertiport capacity, embedded in an online Vertiport Sizing and Capacity tool. We developed the tool primarily to support decision-making for larger airport areas, such as Madrid Airport, which have multiple candidate locations for vertiport placement. The VSC tool enables

airport operators to find vertiport configurations and their capacities based on available areas, their specific shapes, and orientations. Another strong feature of the tool is its flexibility to conduct sensitivity analyses by varying any input parameter. The main feature of the tool is to propose the most favourable vertiport layout for a given area, but unlike previous efforts, we also consider solutions with two layouts for larger areas, merged to allow simultaneous operations, thereby resulting in higher total capacity. One limitation of the tool is that any change to the EASA vertiport design guidelines must be updated in the code. Currently, the FAA uses different vertiport guidelines, and the analysis is not in compliance with them. Similar limitations are related to the set of available vertiport layouts in the VSC tool and the maximum number of FATOs and gates – for any future prominent layouts, an intervention in the code will be needed. These, or any other potential changes that could affect the model, will be addressed accordingly in our future research and tool development.

The vertiport configurations proposed by the VSC tool are used to estimate the cost, which is sensitive to the area and the number of gates equipped with chargers. Additional vertiport-to-terminal is sensitive to vertiport position - landside or airside.

While we rely on existing regulations, academic literature, reports, and extensive consultation with external experts, some assumptions regarding eVTOL operations, costs, and travel times used in this study are estimates and will likely require adjustment for other specific case studies. Stakeholders and other researchers can still rely on the input values and parameters used in this study, but, as a best practice, we recommend adjusting them for the intended application.

Finally, we demonstrate site ranking for Madrid Airport using the SAW method, and compare results obtained with different normalization techniques and weights. Airport operator may use any other preferred Multi-Criteria Decision Making method and/or adjust weights based on experts' knowledge.

By combining qualitative triage with quantitative, sensitivity-driven ranking, the proposed approach supports discussions between airport operators, regulators, and UAM stakeholders, particularly during planning phases when uncertainty remains high and flexible decision support is most valuable.

Regarding the vertiport site selection at airports, most, if not all, directions for further improvement depend on progress in the eVTOL concept of operations and the vertiport regulatory framework. The evaluation and site selection process can be further expanded to include other criteria that may vary across locations, such as FATO utilization concerning wind, the proximity of the Air Traffic Control tower and solar panels, and other obstructions to eVTOL operations, as well as capacity limitations due to electrical infrastructure.

Lastly, in some cases, vertiport integration into the airport environment may come at a significant penalty to runway capacity. For airports

Fig. 16. Ranking MAD candidate sites , equal weights.

Fig. 17. Ranking MAD candidate sites , benchmark vs. Entropy and CRITIC weights.

operating near saturation level, the solution may be to use off-site locations that eliminate interference with aircraft operations. Such locations should be evaluated against other relevant criteria for urban locations, bearing in mind that increasing total travel times will make UAM less competitive than other modes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bojana Mirković: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nikola Ivanov:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dušan Crnogorac:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software. **Matija Sindik:** Writing – review &

editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests..

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Appendix 1. List of acronyms

Term	Definition
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
eVTOL	Electric Vertical Take-off and Landing
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FATO	Final Approach and Take-off Area
MAIA	Multimodal Access for Intelligent Airports
MCDM	Multi Criteria Decision Making
PVC	Propose Vertiport Configuration
SAW	Simple Additive Weighting
TLOF	Touchdown and lift-off area
UAM	Urban Air Mobility
VCA	Vertiport Capacity and Area
VSC	Vertiport Sizing and Capacity

Appendix 2. Vertiport Sizing and Capacity tool: input parameters

Input parameters and their default values adopted in this paper are summarized in Table 6A. They are based on the literature review (Mirković and Sindik, 2024), on relevant parameters for vertiport capacity estimation, as well as a review of vertiport layouts, operational concepts, and design guidelines, relevant for airport sizing.

The dimensions of the selected eVTOL aircraft, relevant for sizing and capacity of the vertiport, were adopted based on eVTOL latest designs, as published on the eVTOL Aircraft Directory on the Vertical Flight Society website (Vertical Flight Society, 2025). Most of the prominent eVTOL aircraft, per Advanced Air Mobility Index (SMG Consulting, 2025a), have a D\D-value of up to 15 m and can seat up to 4 passengers.

For the vertiport design we rely on the latest EASA design rules (EASA, 2022), which assume circular FATO, D-value-based VTOL-capable aircraft

stand (gate) geometry and simultaneous manoeuvring on neighbouring gates (except for pier 1 FATO), and MW-based taxi routes. Table 7A summarizes the physical dimensions of the elements (EASA, 2022), relevant for sizing vertiport options, as well as for calculating average taxiing distances. In addition to this, safe separations between two FATOs (F2F) and between FATO and gates (F2G) allowing simultaneous operations are also included.

Relevant vertiport operations inputs affecting vertiport capacity are final approach and landing time, take-off and initial climb time, engine start/stop time, passenger processing, charging, and taxiing time (derived from the taxiing speed and the taxiing distance).

Passenger processing time (t_{pax}) is a derived value and includes passenger disembarking (t_{demb}) and embarking (t_{emb}) times, which depend on the number of passengers (n_{pax}), as well as on the pre-departure briefing time. As a default value, we assume 30 s per passenger to embark and the same time to disembark. Pre-flight briefing time (t_{br}) is assumed to be 300 s.

$$t_{pax} = n_{pax} \cdot t_{demb} + n_{pax} \cdot t_{emb} + t_{br}$$

Table 6A
Input parameters for the VSC tool.

Parameter	Description	Default value
Vertiport design		
N	number of gates (number of FATOs for multi-functional FATO layout)	2–10
F2F	separation between two simultaneously used FATOs	60 m
F2G	separation between FATO and gate (derived)	9.75 m
eVTOL parameters		
D	D-value	15 m
MW	maximum width	15 m
Seat capacity	number of passenger seats in the eVTOL aircraft (n_{pax})	1
Vertiport operations		
t_{arr}	final approach and landing time	90 s
t_{dep}	take-off and initial climb time	90 s
t_{eng}	engine start/stop time	10 s
t_{pax}	passenger processing time (derived)	360 s
Passenger (PAX) processing		
	PAX disembarking (t_{demb})	30 s
	PAX embarking (t_{emb})	30 s
	Briefing (t_{br})	300 s
t_{ch}	Extra battery charging time beyond the duration of the passenger embarking and briefing time (derived)	53 s
Charging		
	Rate of charge (r_{ch})	0.08 per min
taxi speed	Average taxi speed	5 km/h

To enable fast rotations, which is one of the key requirements for UAM service, we assume that charging of eVTOLs will be allowed during passenger embarking and passenger briefing for the flight. At the given rate of charge (r_{ch}), each vehicle is allowed to be charged for a specific percentage during the turnaround (p_{ch}). In the model, t_{ch} refers to the average extra charging time, i.e., the charging time that exceeds the time required for passenger embarking and briefing. It is derived based on the charging scenario – the percentage of vehicles that require extra charging above the base percentage - p_{evtoli} .

$$t_{ch} = \sum_{i=1}^n \max\left(\left(\frac{p_{chi}}{r_{ch}} \cdot 60 - t_{emb} + t_{br}\right) \cdot p_{evtoli}, 0\right)$$

Charging duration and charging policy may significantly affect vertiport throughput, and there are still many uncertainties related battery charging, capacity, etc. For instance, Macias et al. (2023) use Uber's peak time requirements (Holden and Goel, 2016): undertaking three hours of continuous operation at peak time with only a five-minute recharge in between trips at a 4.8C rate (this means the battery would be fully charged in approximately 12.5 min). Note that in this charging policy, battery never drops below 10 % and does not go higher than 80 % of its capacity.

For default charging scenario in our paper, we assume that 50 % of vehicles are charged above 44 %, which is the percentage charged during passenger briefing and embarking (p_{ch}) at a charging rate (r_{ch}) of 0.08. Of these, 20 % of vehicles are charged to 50 %, 20 % are charged to 60 %, and 10 % are charged to 70 % of the battery. These assumptions return average extra charging time (t_{ch}) 53 s per vehicle under the given charging rate.

Fig. 18A illustrates the six layouts available in the VSC tool. Vascik and Hansman (2019) were the first to introduce satellite, pier, linear, and remote vertiport layouts, inspired by the layouts of existing heliports. Schweiger et al. (2022) propose a linear layout with separated landing and take-off FATOs. Ahn and Hwang (2022) suggest a layout with multi-function FATOs without separate gate areas; multi-function single pad was previously introduced by Northeast UAS Airspace Integration Research Alliance (2021). Note that the same concepts are also used in airport design to differentiate between terminal and apron configurations.

Table 7A
EASA guidelines for vertiport design.

Vertiport element	EASA design specification
Final Approach and Take-off area (FATO)	1.5 x D*
Safety area (SA)	0.25 x D
Touchdown and Lift-off Area (TLOF)	0.83 x D
Taxiway	2 x under carriage width
Ground (GND) taxi route	1.5 x MW
Air taxi route	2 x MW
Gate	1 x D
Gate safety area	0.4 x D

* D-value is diameter of the smallest circle enclosing the VTOL aircraft projection on a horizontal plane, while the aircraft is in the take-off or landing configuration, with rotor(s) turning, if applicable (EASA, 2022).

Most publications related to vertiport sizing and capacity vertiport layouts analyse cases of one or two FATO/TLOFs. In contrast, the number of gates varies from zero to nine (Vascik and Hansman (2019); Preis (2021); Feldhof and Soares Roque (2021)). In the VSC tool, we also use one or two FATOs and between 2 and 10 gates, except in the case of multi-function FATOs, where the number of FATOs equals the number of gates.

Fig. 18A. Six vertiport layouts available in the VSC tool.

Appendix 3. Vertiport Sizing and Capacity tool: capacity and area estimation

The model for vertiport capacity estimation is based on analytical models for estimating theoretical runway and apron capacity and their trade-offs, adapted for vertiport operations and assumed operational policies (FATO, gate, and taxiway can be used by one eVTOL at a time).

For each layout, we calculate arrival, departure, gate and overall capacity. In layouts with two FATOs one FATO is for arrivals, and one FATO is for departures, relatively positioned by design to allow independent eVTOL operations. In this case total FATO capacity is:

$$C_{FATO} = C_{arr} + C_{dep} = \left(\frac{1}{t_{arr}} + \frac{1}{t_{dep}} \right) \cdot 3600$$

In cases with one FATO arrivals and departures, operations are mixed. Capacity is calculated based on the conditions to insert one departure between two arrivals and to allow exchange of eVTOL aircraft across taxiways:

$$C_{FATO} = C_{mix} = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{t_{arr} + 2 \cdot t_{tx} + t_{dep}} \right) \cdot 3600$$

Gate capacity is more complex to assess, as it includes passenger embarking, briefing, disembarking, additional charging, and taxiing to allow one

vehicle to vacate the gate, before next one can occupy it. General equation to calculate gate capacity is:

- For layouts with single FATO:

$$C_{gate} = \left(\frac{N}{(t_{eng} + t_{pax} + t_{ch} + t_{dep} + 2 \cdot t_{tx} + t_{arr})} \right) \cdot 3600$$

- For layouts with separated arrival and departure FATOs:

$$C_{gate} = \left(\frac{N}{(t_{eng} + t_{pax} + t_{ch} + 2 \cdot t_{tx})} \right) \cdot 3600$$

In the formulae above, all times are expressed in seconds, while resulting FATO capacity is expressed as number of operations per hour (gate capacity is measured in aircraft per hour). Overall capacity is derived as minimum of C_{FATO} and $C_{gate} \times 2$ (translating aircraft per hour to operations per hour).

The exception is the case of multi-function FATOs where overall capacity is directly calculated as:

$$C_{overall} = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{N}{(t_{eng} + t_{pax} + t_{ch} + t_{dep} + t_{arr})} \right) \cdot 3600$$

Taxiing time is calculated based on the average taxi distance (d_{tx}) and taxiing speed. Average taxiing distance is dependent on the vertiport layout and requirements for vertiport elements sizing, as defined in Table 8A. Note that there is no taxiing for multi-function FATO.

Table 8A
Taxiing distance calculation.

Vertiport layout	Taxiing distance
Satellite	$d_{tx} = \max \left(2D + (F2G - 0.4D - 0.25D), \frac{D}{\sin \left(\frac{90}{N} \right)} \right)$
Pier with 1 FATO	$d_{tx} = \left(\frac{N-1}{2} \right) \cdot 1.6D + 3D + MW + (F2G - 0.4D - 0.25D)$
Pier with 2 FATOs	$d_{tx} = \max \left(\left(\frac{N-1}{2} \right) \cdot 2D + 3D + MW + (F2G - 0.4D - 0.25D), \left(\frac{F2F + 1.5D}{2} \right) + D + MW \right)$
Linear with 2 FATOs	$d_{tx} = \max \left(\left(\frac{N-1}{2} \right) \cdot 2D + 2D + 2MW, \left(\frac{F2F + 1.5D}{2} \right) + 2D + 2MW \right)$
LEIDT	$d_{tx} = MW + D$

Lastly.

Table 9A summarizes formulae for length (L) and width (W) of the rectangular vertiport area, given vertiport layout and number of gates.

Table 9A
Lengths and widths for different layouts.

Vertiport layout	Length	Width
Satellite	$2D + 2d_{tx}$	$2D + d_{tx}$
Multi-function FATOs	$2D + ((N-1) \cdot (1.5D + F2F))$	$2D$
Pier with 1 FATO	$2D + (F2G - 0.4D - 0.25D) + N \cdot 1.6D + 0.4D$	$2D + \max(2MW, 2D)$
Pier with 2 FATOs	$\max(4D + 2 \cdot (F2G - 0.4D - 0.25D) + N \cdot 2D, F2F + 3.5D)$	$2D + \max(2MW, 2D)$
Linear with 2 FATOs	$\max(N \cdot 2D, F2F + 3.5D)$	$4D + 2MW$
LEIDT	$6D + 4MW$	$N \cdot 2D$

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